

TURN³: Designing and facilitating Problem-Based Learning with the CLARIAH Media Suite

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Deliverable: User requirements list

The following list of user requirements is based on the following elements of the PBL pilot course:

- Learning problem for practical capabilities (Constellation 4 from Savin-Baden, 2014)
 - Learning problem for critical understanding (Constellation 6 from Savin-Baden, 2014)
 - Learning problem for multimodal reasoning (Constellation 7 from Savin-Baden, 2014)
 - Project-led problem-based assessment method: desktop documentary project
 - Pilot tutor manual
- Course evaluation by students and facilitators

Topic	User requirement reflection
<i>Media Suite "Learn" section</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The Learn section contains useful instructions. However, the section could be expanded with a more general introduction to the CLARIAH Media Suite and to archival search strategies in general. There is a lot of rather advanced, specialized, or discipline-specific information, but this alienates and intimidates learners with an interdisciplinary background or with no background in media studies.• A very simple PBL-based Media Suite instruction can easily be developed (see Learning Problem 1) to activate self-directed learning of basic archival skills in a classroom setting. It is recommended that one or more clear tutor manuals are developed to be offered alongside the learning problem, to facilitate teaching basic archival skills in different educational settings, ranging from high school to university education. For the development of the tutor

	<p>manual(s) collaboration between an experienced designer of PBL education and an expert on the Media Suite would be ideal.</p>
<p><i>Search functionality, filtering results, viewing items</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The search functionality implies more transparency than is really achievable. “Facets” are key in streamlining searches, but they are barely explained, and for students first engaging with a media archive, these facets are very difficult to understand and use. • Students are used to searching using Google, and will often formulate their search queries as questions. It would be helpful if there were an instruction about how to search (these) archives; the difference between a search engine query and an archival search query; etc. • There are many dead links: searches often produce long lists of results, only a few of which are actually viewable. This is demotivating to students, which is particularly harmful to the self-directed learning process, which relies for its success even more on student motivation than other forms of learning. It would be helpful if there were a quick way to immediately see which items are viewable, and which are not.
<p><i>Tool criticism</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tool criticism workshop and reflection paper offered by CLARIAH is a bit too complex for undergraduate students with no background in media studies. The questions and exercises assume a rather sophisticated grasp on the interplay between research practices and technologies. It would be very helpful to offer a more basic set of questions and exercises that invite undergraduate learners to engage in (digital) tool criticism. • A tool criticism workshop for undergraduate learners could be developed into a learning problem aimed at activating

	<p>tool criticism through self-directed learning activities. The Desktop Documentary worked well as an assessment tool aimed at testing students' ability to engage with tool criticism. The CLARIAH Learn page could be expanded with a video tutorial on mobilizing the Desktop Documentary as a tool for learning and assessment.</p>
<i>Internationalization</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unfortunately, the Media Suite is barely usable for non-Dutch speaking students. Despite resources on using translation software to search the Media Suite were made available, adding another layer of complexity over the already complicated task of learning to work with archives proved too ambitious (and thus demotivating) for many students. To make self-directed learning with the Media Suite possible in international settings, having at least one (but ideally more) native Dutch speakers per student team is currently an absolute requirement. This begs the question to what extent international students can be expected to have acquired the same level of archival skills as their Dutch team mates at the end of the course. Currently, the lack of internationalization is a major limitation to the usability of the Media Suite for self-directed learning in international settings.
<i>Workspace</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The workspace that the Media Suite offers each user is not amenable to working with a team. Since all forms and constellations of Problem-Based Learning are based on collaboration, the Media Suite should offer the possibility to collaborate in a workspace in order to become more amenable to self-directed learning.
<i>Support</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When students ran into issues that the facilitators could not help them to solve – from technical issues to problems logging in – they were instructed to contact CLARIAH

	<p>Media Suite support via email or via chat. Unfortunately, students often had to wait for days, even weeks, to receive a response. Sometimes they would not receive any response at all. Students were worried about missing deadlines because of this. Since PBL facilitators will often not be experts on all aspects of the Media Suite, for its successful application in educational settings – especially self-directed learning settings – it is important that support is more easily available and accessible.</p>
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